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RARA functions with ROR in lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of a lineage commitment process in the human embryo involving joint function of RARA and ROR.

Citations

1. Zhu, J., Zhou, J., Peres, L., Riaucoux, F., Honoré, N. and Kogan, S., 2005. A sumoylation site in PML/RARA is essential for leukemic transformation. *Cancer cell*, 7(2), pp.143-153.